

Deliverable D8.2: Project website, social media pages and promotional material pack

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Abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation / Acronym	Description
WP	Work Package
EU	European Union
EC	European Commission
CINEA	European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
HE	Horizon Europe - the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2021-2027)
CFS	Certificate of the Financial Statement
VAT	Value Added Tax (a sales tax)
TBC	To be confirmed
GA	Grant Agreement
DMP	Data Management Plan

Project coordinator		
1	PROP	Proplast - Consorzio per la Promozione della Cultura Plastica
Project beneficiaries		
2	POLM	Politecnico di Milano
3	ZOREN	Zorlu Enerji Elektrik Uretim as
4	IRES	IRES - Innovation in Research and Engineering Solutions
5	NORV	Norvento Tecnologia, s.l.
5.1	NNF	Norvento NED Factory, s.l.u. (<i>affiliate partner to Norv</i>)
6	TEK	Fundacion Tekniker
7	EuCIA	Association Europeenne de l'industrie des Composites
8	AEP	AEP Polymers srl
Project associated partners		
9	BUL	Brunel University London
10	ENT	Entelea Ltd

1 Executive summary

This report, D8.2, describes the implementation of the initial branding and communication tools and materials for the EOLIAN project, which will be available at M6. These include the EOLIAN logo and templates, the EOLIAN website, social media pages, project leaflet, and posters. These elements are an integral part of EOLIAN's provisional plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication (D8.1), published at M6, and will help to ensure the project's visibility and facilitate the diffusion of news and results.

The project's brand will present a professional consistent and recognisable identity for EOLIAN, helping to build awareness of the project and facilitate communications activities. The website will serve as the project's central communications hub, providing interested parties with quick access to key project facts, objectives, activities and results, as well as ways to easily contact the project coordination (PROP) and communications and dissemination leader (EuCIA).

EuCIA, leader of WP8: Dissemination and exploitation, will maintain and regularly update the website and social media channels throughout the project. The EOLIAN partners will be strongly encouraged to support these activities, keeping EuCIA aware of their progress and activities, and providing content as necessary. As the project progresses, EuCIA will also update the initial promotional 'starter pack' available at M6 with new materials (posters, leaflets, videos, newsletters etc.) to reach the project's target audiences, according to the communications and dissemination plan.

2 Overview of EOLIAN's communication strategy

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The wind energy industry is committed to enhancing its sustainability by reducing environmental impacts over the complete life cycle of a wind turbine. In a circular economy approach this includes extending the lifespan of wind turbines, improving their recyclability, and minimising waste. As more wind farms are installed new materials and technologies that allow turbine blades to operate reliably for longer, be repaired more easily, and reused or recycled at the end of their service life, are critical.

EOLIAN – *Bio-based, repairable and recyclable vitrimer composites and advanced sensors for highly reliable and sustainable wind blades* – will develop an innovative smart wind turbine blade, manufactured from a recyclable composite material, with in-mould electronics to detect damage early before it becomes a major issue. The EOLIAN blade will provide a step change in how wind turbine blades are maintained, reused and recycled in a circular economy approach.

The EOLIAN project's communication activities will have three main objectives:

- raise awareness with society as a whole and specific audiences and target groups;
- establish synergies with external stakeholders such as national bodies, international agencies and associations;
- create strong visibility using clear, consistent key messages to the scientific and industrial communities.

The project will target a broad range of stakeholders. 14 target groups and 10 key messages have been defined in the communication and dissemination plan (D8.1), together with the planned communications and dissemination channels, tools and activities.

The multimedia promotional package detailed in this report, including logo, website, social media pages, leaflet and posters, will support these communications objectives.

3 Communication tools and materials

3.1 Visual identity (logo & templates)

The **EOLIAN logo** was created at the start of the project. This defines a distinct visual identity for EOLIAN and is designed to improve awareness and recognition across the project's target audiences.

The logo will be used in all communications, including the website and social media channels, project templates (e.g. PowerPoint presentation, report, etc.) and any published or publicly presented material (e.g. leaflets, posters, conference presentations, videos etc.). Graphic elements (charts, infographics etc.) in EOLIAN branding will also be created as the project progresses.

The logo (horizontal and stacked versions) and icon are available in various colours and file formats in the EOLIAN Sharepoint folder: WP Dissemination and exploitation/Starter pack.

Figure 1 Examples of the EOLIAN logo: horizontal format (top), stacked format (lower left) and icon (lower right).

In preference, the green, horizontal logo should be used on a white background. The stacked logo and icon can be used when the horizontal logo may not be suitable (e.g. social media).

The **EOLIAN colour codes** are:

- Light green #DAFDB9
- Dark green #005C52

The **EOLIAN fonts** are:

- Montserrat (headings)
- Open sans (text)

Project templates have also been created for use in internal and external communications activities. The following documents are available in the EOLIAN Sharepoint folder: WP8: Dissemination and exploitation/Starter pack.

- PowerPoint presentation template;
- Word document template for meeting agendas, press releases etc.;
- Deliverables (Word) template.

Figure 2 Cover page of the EOLIAN PowerPoint template.

The templates may be updated, or added to, during the project, according to project and partner requirements.

The project slogan – *A new generation of smart, sustainable wind turbine blades* – will be used in communications materials and messages where appropriate.

3.2 Website

The project's website is **www.eolian-project.eu**.

The website was designed and built by an experienced agency. The site utilises a WordPress content management system. Its performance and load speed are optimised for SEO and mobile viewing (approximately 50% of all web traffic is expected to come from mobile). The website hosting and maintenance plan ensures the site is up to date and secure, and includes technical

support, daily website backups, monthly managed WordPress core updates, plugin updates, theme updates and security updates, performance monitoring, and ongoing website optimisation.

The website build stage was completed in October 2024. Following testing, the site was officially launched on 4th November 2024. It is the central platform for communicating the project's key messages, objectives, and results.

The main objectives of the website are to clearly explain the project concept, methodology and technology solutions, provide news updates about project progress and activities, provide access to all non-confidential project documents and results, and allow stakeholders and interested parties to easily contact the project and register to receive newsletters.

The website has been designed to be attractive and easy to navigate. It currently features seven pages: Home; Project; Partners; News and Events; Media Centre; Publications; Contact Us.

Figure 3 The EOLIAN website homepage.

These pages host the following content.

Home: The homepage will be the most visited page of the site. The slogan – *A new generation of smart, sustainable wind turbine blades* – is displayed prominently at the top of the page. The page goes on to present an introduction to the challenge EOLIAN is intending to answer, the project's key aims, a summary of EOLIAN's end-of-use solutions, and the partners' logos. A Latest News section highlights three recent news stories. Recent news is also showcased in a scrolling band, moving across the page horizontally, adding visual interest.

Project: The project page aims to introduce the project's objectives, activities and expected outcomes in a brief, easily understandable way. It includes several graphics to explain different

aspects of the project e.g. work packages, methodology, and EOLIAN reuse and recycling options. The information on this page can be updated as required as the project progresses.

Figure 4 EOLIAN end-of-use options

Partners: The partners page contains an introduction to each of the 10 partners (company description and logo) and their role in EOLIAN, plus a link to their website. At the top of the page, the locations of each partner are shown on a map of Europe.

The screenshot shows the 'Our Partners' page on the EOLIAN website. At the top, there is a navigation menu with the EOLIAN logo and links for 'Project', 'Partners', 'News and Events', 'Media Centre', 'Publications', 'Contact Us', and a 'Partner Login' button. Below the menu is the heading 'Our Partners'. The main content area features a map of Europe with ten partner logos placed at their respective geographical locations. The logos include: Eoliantec, EOLIA, IRES, TECNIO, norvento energia, Tektiker, and ZORLUENBERG. To the left of the map, there is a text block describing the interdisciplinary consortium.

The interdisciplinary EOLIAN consortium brings together ten organisations from five European countries and includes SMEs, renewable energy companies, research organisations, and an industry association. This complementary team contains experts in vitrimer chemistry, structural health monitoring, composite materials modelling and characterisation, wind turbine blade design and manufacture, and dissemination and exploitation. This allows a holistic approach towards the development of highly durable and circular blades and paves the way for the future successful exploitation of the project's technologies.

Figure 5 The partners location map on the Project page.

News and Events: This page presents a summary (picture and headline) of the project's latest news updates, in date order. The updates are also categorised (e.g. press release, event, blog etc.) to aid understanding. The headline of each update links to the full story on a separate page. The content on this page will build rapidly as it will be regularly updated with project activities and results, interviews, blogs, event attendance, etc. Partners will be strongly encouraged to contribute information to these news updates.

Media Centre: This page is intended as an online 'press kit' where journalists can easily access information about the project for use in their research and articles. The page will include project press releases, background documents on relevant topics (wind energy, wind blade and composites recycling etc.), and images to download. A media coverage section highlighting articles published about the project in key publications, and the project newsletters, will be introduced when these are available.

Publications: The EOLIAN project will provide open access to non-confidential project information. The Publications page provides a download 'library' of the project's published journal research papers, conference presentations, plus non-confidential project reports and Deliverables, and project communications materials (posters etc.). This page will be updated as the project progresses.

Contact Us: This page provides contact details for the project coordinator and the communications team. There is also a form where visitors can send a message to the communications team. The page also includes key facts about the project and the required disclaimer text (explaining views and opinions expressed do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA).

Footers: The footer section of all pages of the website includes a newsletter signup form, contact details for the project coordinator, links to the project's social media channels, the site menu, and the EU logo and funding statement.

A **Partner Login** is available at the top right of each page, linking to the secure EOLIAN Sharepoint site (only partner representatives authorised by PROP will be able to access the Sharepoint via this link).

The website **privacy policy**, **cookie policy** and **terms and conditions** of use are available at the end of each page. A **cookie preference banner** is available on the lower left corner of the page, allowing users to control their cookie settings. The website operates using only essential cookies. Minimal personal data is collected.

Google Analytics has been set up on the website. This allows for anonymous GDPR-compliant visitor tracking and on-page statistics. Website activity and user behaviour will be closely monitored and used to guide content changes if required.

The website will be managed by EuCIA. Initial website updates (from launch in November 2024) will aim at raising visibility of the project and its objectives, ongoing activities, as well as promoting project and partner attendance at events. A series of Meet the Partner articles will commence, highlighting each partner's role in the role.

3.3 Social media

Social media will be a key means of raising the visibility of the project, highlighting key activities and results, engaging with a broad range of stakeholders, and driving traffic to the website.

In the grant proposal the social media networks LinkedIn and X (formerly Twitter) were specified. However, considering that the popularity and usefulness of X is rapidly decreasing, the partners decided to keep only LinkedIn. The EOLIAN LinkedIn page is @EOLIAN project EU. It was created in July 2024.

Figure 6 The EOLIAN LinkedIn page.

The communication plan includes the production of at least three project videos by the end of the project. It is expected that an EOLIAN YouTube channel will be created as soon as content is available, to present the project videos, and potentially relevant partner content.

The addition of further social networks will also be considered according to project needs.

The social media channels will be used to create awareness of the project, communicate progress and results, and build audiences amongst the project's targeted stakeholder groups and the wider public. Wherever possible calls to action (CTA) will be included to drive visits to the website. On LinkedIn posts tags to the project partners will be included wherever possible. Images, infographics and videos will be used extensively since these are known to drive greater engagement. Through the social accounts the project will also aim to build a wide network by interacting with accounts of related EU projects and networks, associations, industry organisations, etc.

Social media followers and engagement will be monitored closely throughout the project and messaging and activities adjusted accordingly.

Partners are encouraged to follow the project account and other partners' social media accounts to build a responsive network to support and amplify the dissemination of approved project content (e.g. press releases, news, events, videos). When posting/sharing project messages a link to the EOLIAN website should be included when possible. The granting authority CINEA can also be tagged: #CINEA, @CINEA - European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (LinkedIn).

3.4 Promotional materials

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In order to disseminate the EOLIAN project, several promotional materials will be prepared: printed leaflets, posters, newsletters and videos. Considering the results, they will be created during the project, especially for use at exhibitions and conferences, targeting the project's main audiences.

Promotional materials artwork will be stored in the EOLIAN Sharepoint folder: WP8 Dissemination and exploitation/Starter pack.

3.4.1 Leaflets and posters

Leaflets and posters will also be available in pdf format for download from Publications page on the project website.

The project's Starter Pack (available at M6) includes artwork for:

- a 4-page leaflet aimed at raising awareness of the project and its goals (published November 2024).
- posters in A4 size for tabletop displays and A1 size for fixing to walls or exhibition panels etc.;
- a PowerPoint presentation providing an introduction to the project, which can be updated and expanded as the project progresses and according to audience requirements.

Print copies of the leaflet will be shared with the project partners for their use at exhibitions and conferences and to distribute to their contacts. Partners should contact EuCIA if they need updated or new materials.

Figure 7 The first EOLIAN leaflet: back and front pages (top image), and interior pages (lower image).

Figure 8 The EOLIAN A1 poster.

3.4.2 Newsletter

A newsletter will be created to promote the project's objectives and activities and share results. Newsletter content will link to further information on the website wherever possible.

A newsletter registration form is available on the website. Registrants will be sent a pdf version of the newsletter. This will also be uploaded to the website and shared with partners to distribute via their communications channels.

When the EOLIAN LinkedIn page reaches 150 followers it will also be possible to create a LinkedIn newsletter for sharing.

The newsletter will be published quarterly, or more frequently, depending on the availability of content.

Updates about key project activities and milestones will also be included in the EuCIA monthly newsletter and on the EuCIA social media channels.

3.4.3 Videos

Videos will be created at regular intervals to showcase the project, the challenges it addresses, its main objectives, the EOLIAN solutions, and the project's progress. All partners will be required to supply input.

The provisional schedule for publication of videos is: M12, M24 and M30.

Videos will be promoted on the project website and social channels.

Project partners will also be encouraged to take short video clips of their project activities and/or technologies, when possible, for sharing on the project's digital platforms.

If sufficient video content becomes available a project YouTube channel may be created.

4 Conclusion

This report describes the implementation of the initial branding and communication tools and materials for the EOLIAN project. These include the EOLIAN logo and templates, the EOLIAN website, social media pages, project leaflet, and posters. These elements are part of EOLIAN's provisional plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication (D8.1), and will help to ensure the project's visibility and facilitate the diffusion of news and results.

All project communication activities (including leaflets, posters, social media, etc.) will acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

www.eolian-project.eu

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